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Critical Analysis of Concept of Biomarkers from Ayurveda Perspective

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Abstract

Today's era of globalization has introduced Ayurveda on a global platform like never before. *Ayurveda* is the ancient life science which aims at leading a healthy life but diseases form an inseparable part of life. All these altered conditions are diagnosed most of the times on basis of clinical features as per *Ayurveda samhitas*. With development of technology the contemporary science uses various biomolecules, imaging techniques in addition to clinical features to diagnose a condition, understand its pathophysiology, monitor the intervention or treatment outcome, these are called as biomarkers. It is necessary for *ayurveda* scholars to get acquainted with this new glossary to face challenges of globalization. In this review article the literature study of modern concept of biomarkers has been made and an attempt is made to envision biomarkers examples mentioned in *ayurveda* literature. Owing to the vastness of *Ayurveda* literature its relevance with modern classification of biomarkers is explained with only a few examples. The article aims at giving *ayurveda* scholars scientific vision while studying *ayurveda* without losing the core of *ayurveda* fundamental principles and willingness to incorporate contemporary biomolecular and imaging techniques advances.

Keywords: Biomarker, *Upamaan Praman, Pratyaksha pramaan, Anumaan pramaan,*

Introduction:

Diseases have been a part of life since time immemorial and continuous efforts are being made to understand the disease process in better way aiming at better intervention and therapeutic results. *Ayurveda* the most ancient science of life has explained the concepts of disease and treatment in short as *Trisutraviz., Hetu, Linga, Aushada skanda* further elaborating it into *Nidan Panchak* viz., *Nidan, Purvarupa, Rupa, Upashay* and *Samprapti*^[1].

While the modern medical sciences describes the diseases under four headings ^[2] :

1. The causative aetiological factors,
2. The developmental mechanism of pathogenesis,
3. Structural morphological changes in the cells and organs and
4. Functional changes.

Biomarkers are such entities that help to understand the biological state of body, which can be measured and help in diagnosing a disease, monitoring its progress and assessing the effectiveness of intervention and /or treatment.

Aim :

Understand the concept of biomarkers and analyze its relevance from *Ayurveda* perspective.

Material And Method:

Classical texts and modern literature is reviewed and critically analyzed to put forth logical interpretation in context to biomarkers.

Review Of Literature :

The term “Biomarker” includes a wide range subcategory of clinical signs and symptoms or distinguished bio-molecule having an important role in different biological and pathological processes. These are objective indications of medical state as observed from outside the patient and tell about a specific pharmacological response to a drug, giving appropriate information about body’s actual condition that can be reproduced and measured accurately ^[3,4]. Thus biomarkers play an important role for

personalized medicine, disease diagnosis, and prognosis.

Ideal biomarker: (‘Biological Marker’) :

An ideal biomarker must possess certain qualities mentioned in figure.1 ^[5, 6].

Figure1: Ideal biomarker: Characteristics.

Classification of Biomarkers:

The biomarkers can be classified on various parameters: figure 2.

Based on Genetic & molecular biology method	Based on Characteristics	Based on Applications- Disease related	Based on Biomolecule
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type 0, • Type 1, • Type 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Molecular, • Histologic, • Radiographic, • Physiological Characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Susceptibility • Diagnostic, • Prognostic, • Safety • Predictive, • Monitoring • Response 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DNA marker, • RNA marker, • Protein based , • Lipid Based, • Sugar based

Figure 2: Biomarker Types Based on Various Parameters

A. Biomarker Types Based on Genetic and Molecular Biology Method:

- a. Type 0 - Natural history markers: Represent clinical indices. Examples -
 - i. Raised ESR value in *Aamvata*^[7].
 - ii. Bio-markers of *Vardhakya* (ageing) like those which determine the biological age i.e. skin elasticity and visual accommodation, those which predict the remaining life expectancy i.e. DHEA-S and hand-grip power, those which determine disease susceptibility, i.e. systolic BP and glucose tolerance test. All these biomarkers can be classified as laboratory tests (eg. blood and urine tests) or as physical tests carried out in a clinic^[8].
- b. Type 1 - Drug activity markers: Used to explain the effect of a therapeutic role. E.g.- Use of Terminal Deoxynucleotidyl transferase – mediated dUTP nick end labeling assay (TUNNEL), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 (ALDH1) to analyze breast cancer chemoprevention effect of *Ashwagandha* (*Withania Somnifera*)^[9].
- c. Type 2 - Surrogate markers: Used as substitute for a clinical end point. E.g.- Traditional *Ayurvedic* doctors used ants for the identification of “sweet urine” in patients^[10].

B. Based on characteristics: Figure 3

C. Based on disease related application – Table 1.

Many of the biomarkers can fall in more than one category based on its application made.

Table 1. Biomarkers classification based on disease related application.

Sr. No	Biomarker Type	Examples
1)	Diagnostic biomarker:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diagnostic biomarker to identify patients with chronic kidney disease - Glomerular filtration rate (GFR) may be used^[11]. • <i>Pratyatmalakshanas</i> of diseases e.g <i>Haridra Netra Mutra Twak</i> in <i>Kamala</i>, <i>Gudena Atidravasaranam</i> in <i>Atiasaara</i>^[12].
2)	Monitoring biomarker:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For assessing whether or not the desired effect of anticoagulation has been attained in patients on warfarin, monitoring biomarkers used - International normalized ratio (INR) or prothrombin time (PT)^[13]. • Assessment of ESR value in <i>Aamavat</i> treatment^[7].
3)	Response biomarker: a. Pharmacodynamic biomarker b. Surrogate endpoint biomarker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For evaluation of warfarin treatment for prevention of thrombosis in a patient pharmacodynamic biomarker used - INR may be used as a^[14]. • Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol reduction is a considered surrogate endpoint for decrease in cardiovascular events and has been used as the basis for ayurvedic herbal anti-hypercholestromia preparations^[15].

Sr. No	Biomarker Type	Examples
4)	Predictive biomarker:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In evaluation of women with platinum-sensitive ovarian cancer predictive biomarkers used -BReast CAncer genes 1 and 2 (BRCA1/2) mutations^[4]. <i>Kapha prakriti</i> person have increased susceptibility to respiratory disorders and obesity^[16].
5)	Prognostic biomarker:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In evaluation of women with breast cancer, to assess the recurrence of breast cancer prognostic biomarkers used- BReast CAncer genes 1 and 2 (BRCA1/2) mutations^[17]. <i>Taila Bindu Pareeksha</i> also helps in establishing prognosis^[18]. Various <i>arishta lakshanas</i> mentioned in <i>Charak Samhita Indriya sthan</i>^[19].
6)	Safety biomarker:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In evaluation of patients on drugs that affect kidney function safety biomarker used to monitor for nephrotoxicity- Serum creatinine^[20]. Changes in myocardial cytoarcitecture to evaluate copper <i>bhasma</i> toxicity^[21]
7)	Susceptibility/ risk biomarker:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To scrutinize individuals with a risk to develop breast cancer susceptibility/risk biomarker used - BReast CAncer genes 1 and 2 (BRCA1/2) mutations^[22]. <i>Kaphaprakriti</i> person have increased susceptibility to respiratory disorders and obesity^[16].

D. Based on biomolecule^[24].

- DNA- based biomarker
- RNA- based biomarker
- Protien based biomarker
- Lipid based biomarker
- Sugar based biomarker

Discussion :

Ayurveda is a holistic science which has basic principles like equilibrium in the components of body like *Dosha, Dhātu, Mala, Agni* affect the functioning of various *srotas* (different systems) and maintain health of an individual. Their normal status or any deflection in the normal status is manifested in form of *lakshanas* (clinical signs and symptoms). *Trividhapariksha* (*Darshan, Sparshana, Prashna*), *Shadvidha Parikasha* (*panch jnanendriya pariksha* and *prashna pariksha*) have been explained in *bruhatrayesto* to assess the status of a person and disease. Selection of treatment is based on *samprapti* (pathogenesis) occurred in patient and cause for particular *samprapti*. Efficacy of treatment is also evaluated in terms of *samprapti vighatana* (reversal of disease condition) which is evident by alleviation of the clinical features manifested. These clinical features encompass both clinical endpoints and biomarkers. Though the term biomarker may be new, the concept isn't de nova to ayurveda - biomarkers mentioned are in form of *lakshanas* and used as objective criterias. *Upamaan, Pratyaksha, Anumaan pramaan* are used for biomarkers explanation. It has been observed that the ancient *acharyas* have tried to explain the complex concepts of pathophysiology and clinical features using *upamana pramana* (similes used). We find innumerable examples of similes given in *bruhatryees* and *laghutrayees* to explain various signs and symptoms too.

The bases of biomarkers in Ayurveda are *panch arthas- Shabda, Sparsha, Rupa, Gandha, Rasa*.

1) *Shabda* – (Sound as parameter)

- Changes in voice of a patient like *Kapotiva kujanam* (stridor) in *apatantraka* patient. – can be used as diagnostic marker.

- Abnormal sounds heard by physician in patient – crepitus in joints of *Sandhigata vata* patient– can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.
- 2) *Sparsha* –(Palpable parameters)
- *Kathina sparsha* in case of *Vataj Vrana* - can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.
 - *Vatapurna druti sparsha* in *Vatodar* - can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.
- 3) *Rupa* –(Visible parameters)
- *Varna* (colour) – yellowish discolouration of nails, eyes in liver disorders - can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.
 - *Sansthan* (clinical features) - Inflammation at joints in arthritic conditions can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.
 - *Rajijanma* (caput medusae) in ascitis - can be used as diagnostic marker, monitoring marker, response marker.
 - *Praman* – liver and spleen enlargement in *yakrutodar* (hepatomegaly) and *pleehodar* (spleenomegaly) respectively etc. can be used as monitoring marker, response marker.
- 4) *Rasa* –(Taste as parameter) Use of various animals is mentioned to interpret indirectly the changes in body fluids of patient.
- Use of ants to analyze urine sugar content can be used as diagnostic marker, predictive marker, and response marker.
 - Use of dogs and crow to differentiate between *shuddha rakta* and *Raktapitta* can be used as diagnostic marker, predictive marker, prognostic marker.
- 5) *Gandha* –(Smell as parameter)
- Various examples are given in *Charak Samhita, Indriya Sthan 2nd* chapter
 - *Related to smell emitted by patient used for prognostic markers.*

Ayurveda literature is full of clinical knowledge and combined with integrated modern biomarker vision will help enhance the scientificity of research and practice. The proper interpretation of these parameters in accordance with the basic principles of Ayurveda can enrich understanding and application of Ayurveda concepts.

The biomarkers can be used for:

- Diagnosing stage of disease
- Prognosis of a disease
- Selection of treatment modality
- Assess treatment efficacy
- Assess ADRs, Toxicity

In clinical settings the disease often has multifactorial etiology which can in turn have innumerable various pathways to exhibit a disease. Treatment outcomes also have variability in respect to doctor- patient relationship, food habits, lifestyle variations from person to person, climate changes, demography, epigenetics posing challenges to select a biomarker. Judicious selection and assessment of appropriate biomarkers will benefit overall patient care.

Conclusion :

- The term biomarker includes objective parameters in clinical setting along with laboratory and imaging investigations.
- Understanding the relationship between measurable biological processes and clinical outcomes is vital.
- Limited information about the types of processes involved in normal physiology of a biological process or pathogenesis of diseases makes constant reevaluation of biomarkers as surrogate endpoints essential.
- Use of biomarkers in Clinical practice & Studies (at least for retrospective analysis of biomarker correlation success) should always have clinical outcomes as ultimate measures, to maximize benefits to patients and reduce harm.
- Use of Clinical findings as Biomarkers and/ or Laboratory and Imaging Biomarkers should be made judiciously for person's/ patient's benefit

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